

Multiscale Observation Services for Mining-related Deposits

Objectives

Environmental Monitoring: create services and tools for a comprehensive environmental impact assessment of mining residues.

Geotechnical Monitoring: develop an integrated service to monitor the critical parameters that control the physical stability of tailings and waste rocks, as well as deploy novel low-impact geophysical methods to capture concealed subsurface processes.

Raw Material Valorisation: develop integrated 3D models for the characterisation of secondary raw resources in mine waste and enable the tracking of stockpiles using time-resolved, multi-scale spectral data.

Methodology

1 MOSMIN services will use Copernicus EO data for time-resolved, spatially extensive, remote monitoring of ground deformation and surface composition. Innovative change detection algorithms will highlight displacements and identify environmental hazards.

2 Satellite data will be integrated with real-time, high-resolution data obtained from unoccupied aerial vehicles and sensors installed at the site, leveraging the power of machine learning for fusion and resolution enhancement of multi-scale, multi-source data.

3 Novel, non-invasive geophysical techniques such as distributed fibre-optic sensing will provide subsurface information to identify potential risks such as internal deformation and seepage.

Figure 1: Illustration of MOSMIN approach to secondary prospectivity mapping and environmental assessments of mine waste. Here, we use EnMap satellite hyperspectral data (acquired on 19 June 2024) to qualitatively map alteration facies at the Rosia Poieni copper porphyry mine, Romania.

Mineral mapping is based on non-linear least-squares unmixing using mineral spectra from the USGS spectral library (Kokaly et al., 2017). Potassic and phyllic facies (B and C) are associated with the highest Cu grades (see Milu et al., 2002), while sulfidic material (F) may be associated with acid mine drainage.

Figure 2: Illustration of MOSMIN holistic approach to deformation analysis of tailings storage facilities. Map shows InSAR surface displacement data (Sentinel-1 data from October 2023 to April 2024), and the consortium's plans for deployment of fibre optic cables (for distributed acoustic sensing), geophones (for ambient noise seismic), and corner reflectors (for enhanced InSAR analysis) at the Trident mine in Zambia.

Pilot Sites

Kevitsa (Finland) Boliden
Aitik & Laisvall (Sweden) Boliden
Roşia Poieni (Romania) CupruMin
Talabre & Ovejería (Chile) Codelco
Trident & Kansanshi (Zambia) FQM

Partners

Coordinators

Sandra Lorenz
Moritz Kirsch
René Booysen
Richard Gloaguen
Trevelayne Faller

Contact

m.kirsch@hzdr.de

